

ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article provides the information why learning the English language is so important these days. There are given some advice from the personal experience of the author, some researches are also explained with proofs. Children have the great ability of doing the things which they like and in this article you can read the ways of teaching the language using children hobbies.

Key words: bilingual, monolingual, age, children, phonemes.

It is true that children receiving a bilingual education may mix two languages during their developmental stages, or may have a lower vocabulary than monolingual children.

However, this is just an intermediate step and eventually you will master both languages and become proficient in both English and Uzbek depending on the situation.

Of course, individual and environmental differences also have a big impact, but it can be said that exposure to both languages from an early age increases the chances of learning to speak both languages like a native speaker.

In addition, in the Uzbek environment where we constantly encounter Uzbek, there is no need to worry that learning English will negatively affect the development of our mother tongue.

I think it's good to start learning English even from the age of 0. Among researchers of second language learning, no one denies that age is an important factor in learning English.

We can say that sooner you learn English, the more effectively you can learn it.

There are different views on the impact of age of onset, such as that children are more adaptable than adults, or that they integrate naturally into a second language environment without analysis.

Among them, the concept of "filtering by native language" has recently attracted attention.

For example, when Uzbek people learn English after a certain age, they often find it difficult to distinguish between sounds that are not present in their native language, for example, they cannot distinguish between the sounds "th" and "r", or they cannot distinguish between the sounds "f" and "th". If your native language is fixed to some extent, you will only be able to process English through an Uzbek filter.

However, it is known that babies up to about 1 year old can flexibly distinguish all the sounds of the languages of the world. This is an infant-only privilege that adults do not have.

Children who start learning English earlier do better on grammar tests

There are some interesting research results. An experiment was conducted (Lin, et al., 2004) to identify English phonemes (minimal pairs) with students from National Taiwan University.

This is the difference between two words that have different meanings, "stone" and "castle", "right" and "light", for example, one phonemic difference, meaning. found that students who began learning English before entering high school were better at distinguishing between phonemes like "R" and "L".

By introducing children to the English language from an early age, they are more likely to acquire the ability to correctly identify phonemes such as "R", "L", and "th".

In addition, increasing the total number of inputs from early English will help improve understanding of English grammar in the future.

Bilingual child care

Children have a wonderful ability to learn on their own what they like. At home, it is important to prepare an environment in which children will love English on their own.

For example, this is one way to use English-language media images effectively. I think it would be good to just select a program that matches the child's stage of development from cartoons, cooking, travel, etc., and leave it on all the time.

If dinosaurs, vehicles, animals, etc. appear, children will find their favorite characters among them. If your child is interested in something, help them show it as a series or collect related CDs or videos. We casually provide materials that children themselves want to hear and see in English.

It's okay if you can't answer the first time. When children understand the need to get out, their awareness of watching programs and videos will change significantly. Gradually, you will be able to concentrate and listen to English, thinking: "I want to talk about this with mom and dad."

I think the key to bilingual childcare is to create a language environment where children can actively input English and output it naturally.

I often hear people say, "I'm not sure about my English" or "I don't speak English in front of my children because my pronunciation is bad." In conclusion, don't worry about it. This is because children can naturally distinguish between sounds that should be imitated and those that should not be imitated.

Let me give you an example from Hong Kong where British English is a good model. In Hong Kong, where many double-income families work, many families employ Filipino maids.

A study published in the Language Science Society on the subject (Leung, 2011) found that children who grew up hearing both Filipino and British phonemes ended up modeling British English.

If children have enough time to listen to native English speakers daily through English language programs and audiovisual materials, children can acquire correct English pronunciation.

So parents don't have to be perfect in English or pronunciation. Even if they are not confident in their English, I would like them to see how adults communicate in English every day.

Seeing adults around you enjoying English will keep you motivated to learn

When I was a child, I became interested in English thanks to my grandmother. I enjoyed watching cooking shows on TV with my grandmother, who spoke some English, and she taught me the meaning of words like "crumbly" and "gooey". I was happy to learn English for food textures like "sweet", "creamy" and "crunchy".

From admiration that "grandmother is cool", I wanted to speak English myself. Seeing adults around you enjoying English, even if it's a dead end, will be an important motivator for kids to learn English.

Selection of learning materials

Choosing educational materials for children with different personalities is a difficult task, but below I have listed three points.

- Content like history is interesting and makes you want to know the future.
- Things that provide a large amount of input and a corresponding amount of output.
- Easy to continue.

In any case, I believe that teaching materials that allow children to come into natural contact with English in their daily lives are ideal, and do not force children to "learn".

For example, CDs and educational videos that can be used while children play are recommended for those who want to start bilingual childcare casually. It would be even better if text could be linked in addition to audio and video.

English input through eyes and ears can be inferred through a toy, or English heard can be read in a picture book and recognized as letters. Children

unconsciously become familiar with the English language by repeating “listen → see → speak → read”. In fact, this "repetition" is very important for learning English in early childhood.

Interests and hobbies of children are diverse and change with age. Parents who are closest to their children should choose the best learning materials for their children in their daily child care.

Benefits of English language

When I was in high school, I spent a lot of time preparing for entrance exams, and I had the bitter experience of not understanding the English spoken by a native speaker in a university class.

As a result of memorizing grammar and words, I was not doing the basic "listening and speaking" activities needed to communicate in English.

I want the children of the future to learn to understand their intentions = “useful English”

This is because even in Uzbekistan there are more and more situations where people from other countries need to use English for business and communication, and the need for comfortable English has never been so high.

In conclusion, the main thing is not to acquire knowledge, but to use English. Proficiency in English or a foreign Language allows you to get away from the world of information limited to Uzbek. By mastering universal English, you can expand your view of the world and gain your own point of view. There is a lot of information that is only available in English or is available faster in English. You can acquire useful English language skills without going abroad. It is not the "knowledge" of the English language that is important, but the "use" of the English language. Especially in a language environment where the main language is Uzbek, it is important to use English consciously.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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